

Supplementary Information: Methods and Additional Results

S1: Method - downscaling of emission scenarios to urban areas

The method for estimating the urban contribution to future global greenhouse gas emissions is comprised of multiple steps. (1) downscaling from native IAM regions to country level and harmonization with historical emissions inventories based on a well-established method (Gidden *et al* 2018); (2) downscaling from country level to grid level with 0.1° by 0.1° resolution accounting for dynamic changes in subnational evolution of GDP and population; (3) calculation of urban emissions on national and regional levels based on gridded projection of urban population; and (4) calculation of urban emissions by city type based on the typology introduced by Montfort *et al.* (2026). They are described in detail in the following.

S1.1 Downscaling and harmonization from native IAM regions to country level

IAMs break down the world into 12-30 macro-regions. Typically, only a few countries are resolved as individual regions in an IAM. We used the *concordia* (<https://github.com/jkikstra/concordia>) tool for downscaling IAM results to country level which incorporates *aneris* (<https://github.com/iiasa/aneris/>) for harmonization with inventory data. This tool takes into account historical country level GHG gas emissions inventory by sector and by species from CEDS ((Hoesly *et al* 2025), as well as country-level socioeconomic projections based on national SSP GDP data (version 3.2). The method used for downscaling the city emissions-relevant sectors (i.e., Buildings, Energy Supply, Industry, Transport, and Waste) is the “*ipat_2100_gdp*” method, meaning a country’s emissions are scaled by national GDP multiplied by the emissions intensity in the base year, with emissions intensity converging between countries within the same region in 2100 (Kikstra *et al* 2025).

S1.2 Downscaling from country level to grid level

To derive gridded projections of future emissions, we apply a pattern scaling approach that integrates (1) information from historical sector-specific emission gridmaps with (2) country-specific projections of sectoral emissions, and (3) gridded projections of proxy variables (population and GDP) used to account for changes in sub-national spatial patterns of socio-economic drivers.

Correspondingly, emissions in sector *i* in grid cell *g* at time *t* is calculated as the following normalized product of (1) country level emissions with (2) fraction of country-level baseyear emissions in grid cell, and (3) socio-economic growth in grid-cell relative to region:

$$E_{t,g,i} = \hat{E}_{t,c,i} \times \frac{\bar{E}_{t0,g,i}}{\hat{E}_{t0,c,i}} \times \frac{P_{t,g}/P_{t0,g}}{P_{t,c}/P_{t0,c}} \times N_{t,c,i} \quad (1)$$

with inputs

- **Historic gridded emissions inventory:**

40 $\bar{E}_{t_0,g,i}$ are gridmaps for sector i in baseyear $t_0 = 2020$ from CEDS (McDuffie et al., 2020) in its latest version v_2025_03_18 (Hoesly et al., 2025), used to capture the sector-specific spatial emissions patterns at t_0 as documented in emissions inventory data set.

- **IAM-scenario based sectoral emissions:**

45 $\hat{E}_{t_0,c,i}, \hat{E}_{t,c,i}$ are emissions in year t and baseyear t_0 , capturing the temporal evolution of sectoral emissions in country R as derived from the country-level downscaling of IAM scenario data as described in 2.2.1.

- **Proxies for dynamic evolution of spatial emission patterns:**

50 $(P_{t,g}/P_{t_0,g}) / (P_{t,c}/P_{t_0,c})$ is the ratio between a proxy variable at grid-level and its country-level average, used to describe changes in spatial emission patterns relative to base-year t_0 . We here use gridded population (buildings, transport and waste) maps (Bondarenko et al., 2025) and GDP maps (for energy and industry; Paprotny (2025)) consistent with the updated socio-economic assumptions at national level used for the quantification of ScenarioMIP-CMIP7 scenarios (see Section 2.3 below).

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- **Normalization factor**

The normalization factor $N_{t,c,i}$ is required to ensure that

$$\sum_{g \in c} E_{t,g,i} = \hat{E}_{t,c,i}$$

60 since $P_{t,g}/P_{t_0,g}$ weighted with $\bar{E}_{t_0,g,i}$ will, in general, not be equal to the proxy value at country level $P_{t,c}/P_{t_0,c}$.

In Equation (1), sprawl of population or economic activity can result in unrealistically high emissions in individual gridcells: If a grid cell transitions from very low GDP or population level at t_0 to substantial value at future time t , the factor $P_{t,g}/P_{t_0,g}$ can become distortingly large (Van Vuuren et al., 2007). To avoid such distortions, we (1) introduce minimum
65 population and GDP levels in the grid cells, and (2) identify newly developed grid cells and assign them the country's average sectoral emission intensities. As for (1), we assume a minimum population level of 0.01 per 100 km², and a minimum GDP level of 1 \$ per 100 km² in cells with non-zero population or GDP. Globally, these minima only create 800 additional population (~10⁸ times less than the global population), and 9000 USD more (~10⁹ times
70 less than the gross world product) over all time-steps, so they have a negligible impact on aggregate quantities. As for (2), we classify any grid-cells above the threshold of three-fold increase in proxy value $P_{t,g}/P_{t_0,g} > 3 \times P_{t,c}/P_{t_0,c}$ as newly developed, and assume sectoral emissions to correspond to the national per-cap emissions intensity (buildings and waste), or sectoral per-GDP emissions intensity (energy supply, industry and transport). A
75 sensitivity analysis (Supplementary Figure S3) shows that downscaling results are robust to the choice of threshold for classification as newly developed, and the minimum population and GDP levels.

80 ***S1.3 Aggregation from grid to city level using demographic projections from FuturePop***

The attribution of emissions to urban, peri-urban or rural areas is based on gridded population datasets from World-Pop for historical data and Future-Pop for projections by SSP until 2100. Urban and peri-urban emissions are weighted based on the respective population share in each grid cell, which means that a cell does not need to be classified as exclusively belonging to one urbanization class. Data was obtained via processing as part of the Exposure datasets of the COMPASS project (Paprotny 2025).

85 ***S1.4 Re-Aggregation to country level, regional and global urban contributions to emissions, and analysis by city types.***

90 Sectoral emissions data is reaggregated from grid-level to the original scenario regions, tests verifying the consistency with the original IAM data. The same is done for the urban and peri-urban emissions grid of each sector and their share of total sectoral emissions calculated.

95 To incorporate urban typology information, we adopted the four data-driven city types proposed by Montfort et al. (2026) based on the Global Human Settlement Layer Urban Centre Database. These types characterize cities in terms of development stage, growth and expansion patterns, infrastructure conditions, and climate-related pressures. In this study, we refer to these four types as emerging, rapidly growing, established, and megacities. Emerging cities correspond to smaller, lower-income cities with limited infrastructure, low human development, and high cooling needs; rapidly growing cities represent economically growing cities with intermediate infrastructure, low population density, and rapid horizontal expansion; established cities encompass wealthier cities with strong infrastructure and limited population and economic growth; and megacities refer to high-density, fast-growing cities with relatively advanced infrastructure but acute cross-sectoral pressures.

100 To align the original classifications with our analysis grid, we applied a population-weighted spatial aggregation approach. Urban-centre polygons were linked to their corresponding city-type labels and rasterized. To preserve the socioeconomic attributes of small urban centres as completely as possible, while accounting for potential local spillover effects of urban economic characteristics driven by geographic similarity, we applied an all-touched rasterization rule. Where multiple city types intersected the same 0.1° grid cell, the final classification was assigned to the type capturing the largest population-weighted contribution within that cell. This produced a gridded city-type mask spatially consistent with our analytical framework while retaining the original city-level typological information.

S2 High-resolution gridded socio-economic projections

115 Our approach relies on gridded projections of population, the urban share of population, and GDP. The data was created by combining multiple sources, described in detail in the documentation accompanying Paprotny (2025).

S2.1 Population

120 Gridded population in 30 arc second resolution was obtained from the WorldPop/FuturePop
dataset (Bondarenko *et al* 2025a, 2025b) (Bondarenko *et al.* 2025a,b) and harmonized at
national level with UN World Population Prospects (United Nations 2025) (United Nations
2024) until 2023 extended with SSP v3.2 (IIASA 2025) (IIASA 2025) afterwards. For some
125 small countries and territories, the SSP projections are not available, hence SSP regional
aggregates were used instead to extrapolate historical population (the same applies to GDP
projections in 2.3.3).

For constructing population projections for 2025–2100 at 5-year steps, WorldPop Global2
R2025A (Bondarenko *et al.*, 2025a) provided 1 km population distributions for 2015–2030,
along with subnational population shares (proportions of each country's population in each
130 GADM admin-2 unit) (GADM 2012). Global2 data for 2015–2025 measured, per admin unit,
(1) the fraction of grid cells becoming new built-settlement in each 5-year interval and (2)
average people per new built-settlement cell; these rates were extrapolated beyond 2025
and combined with a probability-of-transition surface from the Built-Settlement Growth Model
(BSGM Nieves *et al* 2020), which ranks non-settlement pixels by transition likelihood. For
135 each future 5-year step and admin unit, high-probability pixels were selected to convert to
built-settlement, extending urban footprints via observed local expansion/infill dynamics. The
baseline WorldPop grid was then populated with people in new urban pixels using these
estimated persons-per-new-cell rates, followed by normalization to (1) match SSP national
totals exactly and (2) preserve baseline admin-2 proportions - yielding consistent 1 km
140 projections where urban areas expand and densify per historical patterns.

S2.2 Urban share of population

To classify the population according to the urban-rural spectrum, the population count grid at
30 arc seconds was converted into population density. Then, the built-up surface grid from
the Global Human Settlement Layer GHSL (Pesaresi *et al* 2024) was obtained for 2020-
145 2025 at the same resolution, and further extrapolated into the future proportionally to
population change at grid level. Then, we applied the Degree of Urbanization (DEGURBA)
methodology (European Commission, Eurostat 2021, Dijkstra *et al* 2021) to classify grid cells
into cities, towns (incl. suburbs) and rural areas. The conversion is not perfect as the original
methodology uses a regular 1 km grid, while here we use a geographical grid of only
150 approximately the same size. However, the results are still closely aligned to the results of a
DEGURBA-based dataset from GHSL for the historical period (Schiavina *et al* 2025),
especially for cities. The differences for towns are mostly due to a different population
disaggregation in WorldPop compared to GHSL. In this study we refer to the aggregate of
DEGURBA cities and towns/suburbs as urban areas.

155 S2.3 GDP

National-level GDP data until 2023 was primarily obtained from United Nations Statistics
(2025), amended with country-specific sources. The timeseries was extended into the future
with SSP v3.2 projections. For 82 countries with historical subnational GDP data
(representing about 89% of global GDP), the national-level data was first disaggregated
160 according to variation in GDP per capita among the 2652 subnational administrative

divisions within those countries. For the future projections, the latest available distribution of subnational GDP per capita was used. The data was compiled from 127 different sources (see Paprotny 2025 for details). Finally, the GDP was distributed into the grid in 60% proportionally to gridded population and 40% proportionally to built-up surface. This ratio was chosen to approximate the typical relative contributions of labour and capital inputs to GDP (see, e.g., Arpaia *et al* 2009, Guerriero 2019)Arpaia et al. 2009, Guerriero 2019).

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S3 Supplementary Figures

225 **Supplementary Figure S1:** Urban contribution to gross GHG emissions from the Waste, Buildings, Transport, Industry and Energy Supply sectors, as well as total gross GHG from these sectors (dashed) for the full set of ScenarioMIP marker scenarios. CDR includes non-urban contribution.

Gross GHG, excl. Bunkers, AFOLU, CDR [GtCO₂e]

Supplementary Figure S2: Urban contribution to gross GHG emissions from the Waste, Buildings, Transport, Industry and Energy Supply sectors for the full set of ScenarioMIP marker scenarios.

Sensitivity Analysis

Supplementary Figure S3: Sensitivity analysis varying downscaling parameters. First Row: Threshold for classifying a grid cell as “newly developed” (default 3). Second Row: Minimum values for cells with non-zero values for proxy population and GDP (default 1). Third Row: emission gridmaps used for the downscaling (default CEDS, sensitivity EDGAR).

250 **Supplementary Figure 4:** Global emissions maps of CO2 emissions (excl. bunkers, AFOLU and CDR) for 2020, and 2050 *Medium*, and 2050 *Very Low*.

255 **Supplementary Figure 5:** Regional maps of total CO2 emissions grid for 2020, and 2050 *Medium*, and 2050 *Very Low*.

